

SCHOOL INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP OF FAR-FLUNG SCHOOLS IN THE NEW NORMAL

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Abstract: The purpose of this case study was to have an in-depth understanding of the instructional leadership of the elementary school head of Tupi South District. The current study was done within the qualitative framework, employing a case study design for which six (6) participants who were working in different settings were chosen through purposive sampling and were interviewed. The audio-recorded interviews were transcribed and analyzed using qualitative template analysis, and the merging themes were noted. The study showed, among others, that elementary school heads face several problems, difficulties, and challenges in this new normal setting. The participants responded also that there were various problems met in their function as instructional leader. Parents and learners' participation were also given an importance during the conduct of the study. It reflected that their participation and coordination in school have a huge contribution to the success of the implementation of Self-Learning Modules as curriculum instruction. The result of the study could not generate a generalization of the experiences of the participants. To view the participants' idea on how they analyzed their role as an instructional leader, they reflected it as inspiring others, providing support, and to be an effective role model. Lastly, to determine the extent of the problem and provide interventions to address such, other research methods may be deemed beneficial.

Keywords: educational management, instructional leadership, far-flung schools, new normal, case study, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

The work of the school head is complex, as described; it involves different areas regarding essential things that surround its function and it becomes more difficult as schools enter the new standard era during this pandemic. Even when the physical environment and learning process change, school leaders must be more adaptable in managing school resources. They are also likely to be more complex in decision-making that was not needed before.

As mandated by IATF (2021), it is discouraged to engage in face-to-face activities, and using of social media platforms serves as the central issue in this new typical setting. One of the most affected parts of school management is the instructional leadership of every school head. The health concerns about their faculty, staff, and students also added to their frustrations. It is a burden for them to ensure that their students get a quality education without risking the health of everybody.

Moreover, this academic year is drastically different from the previous one. The epidemic ushered forth many reforms across the board, most notably in schooling. The way a school operates has a significant impact on the lives of all

students. Student accomplishment was one of the most critical elements that stood out. By shifting the mode of instruction from face-to-face to modular or online classes, changes somehow bring unfavorable effects to school instructional leadership. In this school year, the school heads' main goal is to promote learning and see a better outcome even the school is struggling. With cutting-edge academic planning tools, administrators created a personalized learning plan with goals and task links to meet the precise requirements of students to learn (Grissom, 2021).

Furthermore, in Tupi South District, this scenario also burdens the schools. The majority of primary schools in this area are far apart, making internet gadgets and transportation challenging to come by. Typically, school leaders and instructors assigned to these locations do not live in the school's neighborhood; some of them reside in the municipality and city that surrounds them. Additionally, the Tupi South district applies modular printed instruction to the pupils in this new normal. The teacher's communication with the pupils and parents is too limited and the only way to contact them is through the house-to-house visitation that could not be conducted every day. School heads working in these demanding and chaotic circumstances are relentless, and their opinion is limited. Also, student outcome and delivery of instruction may vary from schools located in low lands where all access to communication and mobile apps applies to those in far-flung and high lands with no internet connection.

The Rationale of the Study

This study was conducted to measure the changes made in school leadership during the pandemic. The elementary school principals at Tupi South District schools are struggling to adjust to their new normal. The school principal made their management approaches and adjustments to meet the job's demands without jeopardizing the system's personnel and members. The internet and cellphone connections are too difficult to access at the research location, where schools are located in far-flung and inaccessible places. Transmitting information from one to another was the main issue in leadership styles. School heads' burden was not only focused on school and staff development but closely on ensuring the health safety of everybody against the virus.

During the new standard, school heads of Tupi South District elementary schools expect to cope with different changes in instructional leadership. The pandemic brought extended the actual scope of their responsibilities and extended their burden. The study focuses on the impact of changes made by pandemics on the instructional leadership of different elementary school heads of Tupi South District elementary schools.

Theoretical Lens

Tony Bush's theory of instructional leadership was anchored in this study. This theory of Bush described instructional leadership as one of the most enduring constructs in the shifting typology of leadership models. They view instructional leaders as the primary source of knowledge

for developing their educational program. They give importance to the effort of school heads to work with staff to win support and high commitment, to improve workplace condition, to resolve conflicts, and to enhance the trust of colleagues (Pan et al., 2015; Ng, F., 2019; Smith, G., 2017)

Moreover, the part of the school head's function was greatly affected during the new typical setting, especially in far-flung areas but there are several considerations on implementing activities in school. Schools must consider the success of learners' achievement without risking the health of everybody. On the other hand, instructional leadership refers to a school head's ability to respond to changing circumstances. Nonetheless, due to the extraordinary events that occur around the globe, instructional leadership in this new normal has developed as one of a kind. Thus, school heads were encouraged to become more digital, mainly communicating with their teachers, students, stakeholders, and others.

In this new normal, however, the instructional leader should be an effective instructional decision-maker, which means that a leader must be capable of understanding students' requirements and formulating the best or less harmful judgments (Domingo et al. 2021; Fleming et al., 2019)

Research Question

The study aimed to provide an in-depth description and analysis of school instructional leadership of far-flung schools of Tupi South District in the new normal.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Specifically, it answered the following grand tour questions:

1. How does the instructional leadership of public-school heads of far-flung schools of Tupi South District be described?
2. How do the changes impact the instructional leadership of the participants?

2. PROCEDURES

The Rationale of the Qualitative Research

Qualitative research focused on the interpretation of the perception of people from a social perspective using various qualitative data collection tools, including interviews, social queries, polls, or surveys. The result of qualitative research tends to be primarily descriptive. Proper integration of qualitative research is essential to conduct an in-depth study on any social or educational phenomena based on participants' views. Qualitative research helps build meaningful relationships between the researcher and ordinary people, which facilitate a better understanding of their world and interpret the result in terms of a qualitative approach (Creswel et al. 2017; Sieber et al. 2018).

Research Design

This research used a qualitative case study as a research design. It is an in-depth study of a particular research problem rather than a statistical survey. It is often used to narrow down a vast field of research into one or a few easily researchable examples. The case study research design was also helpful for testing whether a specific theory and model applies to phenomena in the real world. It is a good design when not much is known about a phenomenon.

Moreover, according to Thomas (2021), a case study is an in-depth examination of the intricacy and uniqueness of a situation from different viewpoints. A case study is an in-complexity investigation of a person, a group of individuals, or a unit intended to be generalized across numerous disciplines. Intensive, systematic research of a particular individual, group, community, or division is also said. In this research, the researcher examined in-depth data relating to several variables and explained how case studies were applied to better understand complicated phenomena in the natural world. Indeed, employing case studies in research allowed adopting the holistic character of the participants.

Furthermore, when describing the steps undertaken while using a case study approach, this research method allowed the researcher to take a broad and challenging topic or phenomenon and narrow it down into a manageable research question(s). By collecting qualitative or quantitative datasets about the phenomenon, the researcher gained more in-depth insight into the phenomenon than obtained using only one type of data. In a specific study, the researcher used multiple case studies (Gammelgaard, B. 2017; Tetnowski, J. 2015; Houghton et al. 2015)

Samples and Site

The sample size utilized in qualitative research methods was frequently smaller than that used in quantitative research methods because qualitative research methods were often concerned with garnering an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon or are focused on meaning and heterogeneities in essence (Shaheen et al. 2019;). In this study, in-depth interview work was not as involved with generalizing to a larger population of interest and does not rely on hypothesis testing. Instead, it was more inductive and emergent in its process.

Meanwhile, the target participants of this study were only elementary school heads, particularly assigned in far-flung areas. Tupi South District has four elementary schools in the lowlands and six in the highlands and the far-flung regions; these were Juan Loreto Tamayo Extension, Acmonan Integrated School Kafok Extension, Glandang Elementary School, Benigno Integrated School, Balisong Elementary School, Miasong Elementary School.

Furthermore, purposeful sampling identified as purposive and selective sampling was a technique that the researcher used to engage participants who can deliver in-depth and detailed information about the fact under investigation. It was highly defined by the qualitative researcher generating the qualifying criteria each participant must meet to be considered for the research study (Palinkas et al. 2015).

Access and Permission

Before conducting the research, the researcher gave an effective action plan to protect the involved participants. All participants were required to sign two consent forms before proceeding to the study. The first informed form provides a

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

detailed description of the research and the data collection process; participants were also notified of their rights to withdraw from the study at any time.

Moreover, the second form was the consent form with the confidentiality agreement between the researcher and the participants. This form contained a written narrative of the researcher's responsibility to maintain confidentiality prior, throughout, and following the research study.

In addition, the data collection process took place simultaneously and in a suitable location for each participant. Participants might quickly sign consent papers at the first location. The next meeting was private and confidential, where participants could take the interview questions. It took place after working hours, or any time the participants could not be pressured to attend (Tracy, S. J. 2019).

Data Gathering Strategies

Qualitative data collection approaches were exploratory and mainly concerned with gaining insights and understanding underlying reasons and motivations. Qualitative data collection methods emerged after it became known that traditional quantitative data collection methods could not express human feelings and emotions. Popular qualitative data collection methods used in education studies include interviews, focus groups, observation, and action research (Sutton et al., 2015; Moser & Korstjens, 2018). The researcher gathered data from the participants by employing an in-depth interview. By doing this, the researcher personally went to the respective schools where the participants were assigned and asked permission from the Public School District Supervisor to allow the conduct of the study. Finally, the researcher asked for consent from the participants to allow the recording of the in-depth interview with audiotape to become more credible.

Data Analysis Approach

Template analysis used the development of a coding template that summarizes themes identified by the researcher as necessary in a data set and organizes them in a meaningful and helpful manner. Using broad themes like responses to disease,' hierarchical coding is stressed, with broad themes like 'changing connections,' embracing narrower, more detailed ones like 'changed relationships with health professionals,' and so on. Analysis often starts with some a priori codes, which identify themes strongly expected to be relevant to the analysis. It emphasized the use of hierarchical coding but balances a relatively high degree of structure in the process of analyzing textual data with the flexibility (King et al. 2018; Brooks et al. 2015; Gammelgaard, 2017).

Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

The relationship and intimacy between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns. Qualitative researchers faced dilemmas such as respect for privacy, establishing honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Ethically challenging situations may emerge if researcher must deal with contradicting issues and choose between different methodological strategies in which conflict arises (Roberts, L. D. 2015).

In such cases, disagreements among different components such as participants, researcher, researcher's discipline, the funding body, and the society may be inevitable. Some significant ethical concerns that should be taken into account while carrying out qualitative research are anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent (Collins et al. 2018)

Moreover, integrity is honesty and goodness within qualitative research and underpins ethical practice in all the data collection and analysis activities. It may be assumed as a sort of straightforwardness or moral uprightness' that rejects willful duplicity and dishonesty, and the researcher's openness and completeness define it. Integrity is central to ethical research principles that focus on the responsibility of researchers not to harm, gain informed consent from participants and represent respondents' views as accurately as possible as part of the epistemological process.

On the other hand, the term 'confidentiality' conveyed different meanings for the researcher. Except in the case of specific healthcare practitioners, confidentiality implies that no personal information is shared. The responsibility of secrecy for researcher, on the other hand, was less obvious, and it entailed clarification of the type of conclusion that may be expected from the study.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The researcher must endeavor to minimize the possibility of intrusion into the autonomy of study participants. When sensitive issues are concerned, children and other vulnerable individuals should have access to an advocate present during the initial phases of the study, and ideally, during data-gathering sessions. It is sometimes necessary that the researcher clarifies in writing which persons can access the initial data and how it might be used (Thomas, G. 2021; Tracy, S. J. 2019).

3. FINDINGS

This chapter presents the findings, which describe individuals in the study and analyze themes.

Description of Individuals

Tupi South District's six elementary school heads assigned in far-flung areas were the study participants. Because their schools are so far apart, the researcher visited them individually rather than gathering them in one location. The inclusion criteria consisted of the Elementary School Head of Tupi South District assigned to far-flung schools based on the given attributes. Length of service and position/designation may vary as long as the informant has adequate knowledge to discuss their lived experiences as school head to the most recent years.

The first participant is a 37 years old female elementary school principal from Juan Loreto Tamayo Extension, a small I.P. school composed of 131 pupils and eight (8) teaching staff. She holds a Master's degree in education with a concentration in Educational Management. Juan Loreto Tamayo Extension is found on Sitio Kitubo, Miasong Tupi, South Cotabato.

The second participant is an elementary school head of Acmonan Integrated School Kafok Extension, an indigenous school with 88 population and considered a small school. It is also the first school she led. She served as school head in three and eight months, a female and 38 years of age, and completed her CAR-MMEM. Her school is located in Sitio Kafok, Acmonan, Tupi South Cotabato. As of now, the school is composed of five teaching staff.

The third participant is the principal of Glandang Elementary School in Tupi South Cotabato's Sitio Glandang Barangay Kablon, with 88 pupils and seven teachers. A 40-year-old gentleman holds a master's degree in education focusing on educational management. He has worked as the school's principal for the past five years.

The fourth participant is a school head of Benigno Integrated School found in Benigno, Miasong, Tupi South Cotabato, the farthest school in Tupi South District. She is 48 years of age and spends five (5) years as school head. Benigno Integrated School has a total population of 202 learners, both elementary and secondary.

The fifth participant is an elementary school head of Balisong Elementary School found in Sitio Lemblisong Kablon Tupi South Cotabato. He is 39 years of age and a graduate of MAED. He already spent fourteen years in Deped as a classroom teacher and five (5) years as Head Teacher. Balisong elementary school is a small I.P. School with 176 total population and eight (8) staff.

The sixth participant is an elementary school head of Miasong Elementary School. He is already 56 years old, with 22 years' experience in Deped and nine (9) years as school head. He aimed his master's degree as Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management with complete academic requirements

Analysis of Themes

Table 1: Thematic Analysis of Participants on how instructional leadership is described.

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Experience of School Head in Delivering Instruction A. Way of Delivering of Instruction 1. It is a combination of face-to-face and virtual. 2. It depends upon the situation. 3. Sometimes via text messages was applied. 4. Apply the use of text messages and group chats to avoid contact with others 5. Personal connections must always be avoided, according to IATF regulations. 6. It should be face-to-face.	1. Situational and optional 2. Obedience 3. Traditional

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

<p>B. Problems met in delivering instruction</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. It is easy to deliver my instruction due to the few numbers of teachers and staffs. 8. I need to adopt changes brought about by a pandemic. 9. I need to find ways to alleviate the demand for new normal. 10. I need to consider health issues all the time. 11. Need to deliver instruction face to face due to lack of gadgets and electricity. 12. Social media is not possible in school. 13. Parents have no cellphones. 14. Some houses have no electricity and other devices for communication. 15. I need to deliver it face to face without risking their health. 16. Many things to be considered 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Manageable 5. Mindfulness 6. No internet access 7. Lack of gadget 8. Risk-taking
<p>C. Problems Encountered in Implementation of Self-Learning Modules as Curriculum Instruction</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 17. Only a few parents who continuously get the modules 18. Some modules and assessments do not have answers. 19. Modules were delivered house to house due to the negligence of parents. 20. Parents have no time to teach their children to answer the modules. 21. Mostly of parents belong to poor educational status. 22. The issue of teachers' printing was brought up. 23. Teachers' family member is complaining about the burden of printing modules. 24. Teachers suffer from late or non-submission of modules. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Inattentiveness 10. Uneducated 11. Burdensome
<p>D. Ways of overcoming difficulties</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 25. Constantly monitor the production and distribution of modules. 26. Make sure that all printing materials are provided. 27. The proportion of printers purchased to the number of teachers. 28. She solicited printing materials to different stakeholders to ensure that everything was provided. 29. Constant communication with parents 30. Conduct home visitation regularly to parents. 31. Conducted orientations on sitio about the importance of modules. 32. Conducted meetings with parents to disseminate information properly. 33. MOOE was utilized correctly and transparently by all teachers and parents. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Supervision 13. Provision 14. Raising funds 15. Strong Communication 16. Transparency
<p>E. Monitoring Learner's Progress</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 34. Teachers gave a monthly monitoring plan. 35. Teachers submitted class monitoring tools of learners. 36. Through the results of the instructors' assessments of the students. Through meetings with teachers to validate their reports. 37. Conducted round table suggestions with teachers. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 17. Teacher-based reports 18. Close Supervision
<p>F. Monitoring Parents' Participation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 38. Conducted parents meeting of parents every month 39. Guided regular sessions with parents 40. Gather them for an informal meeting 41. An established good relationship with parents through text if possible. 42. Spend time for home visitation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 19. Formal and informal meetings 20. Build a good relationship

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

<p>G. Giving of Praise and Appreciation</p> <p>43. During meetings, they appreciate teachers.</p> <p>44. It is giving certificates for those learners who have excellent performance.</p> <p>45. It is giving certificates of appreciation and commendation to those parents who are participative.</p> <p>46. They are sharing ideas with them.</p> <p>47. We were leaving notes of appreciation every day.</p> <p>48. Considering everybody as a member of the group</p> <p>49. Always giving them words of encouragement.</p> <p>50. They were sharing with them their daily success.</p>	<p>21. Verbal Appreciation</p> <p>22. Intangible rewards</p> <p>23. Giving Sympathy</p>
<p>H. View as Instructional Leadership described</p> <p>51. Difficult but need to capacitate</p> <p>52. It is tough to impose my instruction, and it needs to consider the health of everybody.</p> <p>53. It needs to consider the solution to every problem during the sudden changes.</p> <p>54. It has brought up a slew of issues that must be addressed.</p> <p>55. It is very challenging because I need to address every problem referred to me as school principal.</p>	<p>24. Difficult</p> <p>25. .Challenging</p>

Situational and Optional

Good relationships among school heads and teachers, teachers to parents, contributed a big part to the development of the school. And it could be possible with proper and effective instructional leadership. Using mobile and internet application help deliver instruction easily and fast. But the availability of this matter is not applicable or sometimes limited in some schools located in far-flung areas. For this reason, the school head would only depend on the availability of the mode to be applied. Sometimes, it is possible to use a mobile app if no disruption happens, like heavy rains and others. Even face-to-face is discouraged; the school head has no option but to take it. The most exemplary ideas for educating students to come from far-flung regions where internet connection is limited, and Facebook has drained all personal and contextual resources (Tria, J.Z. 2020; Uko et al. 2015; Mohiuddin, 2017). As quoted:

"The mode of delivering of my instruction is a combination of face to face and virtual depending upon the situation since the number of teachers is just manageable." (P1 L 8-10)

"In this new normal, my delivery is sometimes via text message but always face to face with proper health protocol" P3 L 273-274

"In school, I disseminate my instruction through limited face to face. I also apply the use of messenger, text and group chats if the connection is available." (P5 L 546-547)

Obedience

This school year is very different from the past years. School heads put at the top of consideration the health safety of individuals as mandated by AITF and Deped. This statement reflects on D.O. no.014 s.2020, following the guidelines on the Required Health Standard in Basic Education Offices and Schools. Education in the new normal is a shift of learning space from public space to personal freedom, as one of the participants stated that it is essential to follow the guidelines set by Deped and IATF to avoid taking the risk (Abdirasulov, J. 2021; Bafadal et al. 2018; Shufutinsky et al. 2020). The participant said:

"...we follow the safety protocols set by IATF making sure that everyone is safe.....the mode of instruction given to the teachers was based on the standards set by Deped in this new typical scheme." (P1 L 10-11)

Traditional

Internet connectivity, mobile app, and other sources of media help lessen the burden of communication and improve the teaching-learning process. Deped aims to establish 21st-century teachers and learners. But there are still schools in the locality of my study which do not have any internet access, no signal to any network and even the worst no electricity yet.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The only way of delivering instruction is through face-to-face. According to the discussion, adverse changes in employee relations and views toward the organization may emerge when communication is impossible. Based on this, the school head needs to exert another source to employ strong communication with the school staff (Guardacasa et al. 2020; El-Sofany et al. 2020; Ter Hoeven et al., 2020). As quoted:

"In the delivery of my instruction, it should be face to face. I had no other option since internet connectivity is not available on the site of our school." (P2 L145-147)

"In our school, there is no other way of delivering my instruction but face to face" (P4 L 410-41)

"In our school, I disseminate my instruction through the limited face." (P5 L 546).

"The mode of delivering my instruction is limited face to face. Virtual delivery is impossible due to absence of internet connection in our place." (P6 L 676-677).

Manageable

Dealing with a small group is better than handling the large one. There are few people and easy to handle. Fewer teachers, fewer learners mean fewer human resources to manage. During this new normal, being in a small group is an advantage. Following DepEd order No. 14 s. 2020 emphasized that the conduct of large physical gatherings might not be possible and restricted (Ter Hoeven et al. 2020; Mahapatra et al. 2021; Collie, R. J. 2021). In support of this description of how the participants view herself, she quotes the following:

"So far, I did not find difficulties of delivering my instruction to my teachers because of our few numbers, and we are only five and easy to handle." (P2 L 152-153)

Mindfulness

Leaders need to adapt quickly to a rapidly changing situation—the new standard needs school leaders who are ready to undress old mindsets while upholding values and ethics. School leaders are at the forefront of the scenario. To keep up with constantly changing norms and situations, school leaders must be more flexible in managing school resources this time. They must be prepared, competent, and futuristic (Ancho, I.V, 2020, Fiarman, S.2017; Mart, C.T, 2917). As quoted:

"I need to find ways to deliver it face to face without risking the health of everybody, especially my teachers." (P3 L 283-25

"I need to adjust and adapt changes in my leadership styles." (P1 L 17)

No Internet Access

The mobile communication system can ensure command and contrast and other information transmission in mobile warfare. Using the internet in delivering instruction is an effective tool and the fastest way of disseminating information that schools in urban places apply. But the participant of this study looks at this matter as a problem in delivering instruction since in their schools, and there is no internet connectivity (Jia et al. 2021; Cho et al. 2019; Valikangas et al. 2020). In detail, the following is the participant' statement:

"It also takes a day to deliver my instruction since social media and other means of communication are not applicable in our school." (P4 L 419-420).

Lack of Gadget

Due to the mobile phones and the many feature-oriented applications, students can learn at their pace and take their time and understand things, as everything is just a click away. But this concept was hard to achieve in some remote places. Aside from the lack of internet access, the participant's concern is the lack of devices for communicating with their parents. Cellular phones nowadays are very common to us and the most effective tool for communication. We already consider it one of our basic needs like food and shelter. And lack of these gadgets becomes a problem for school heads in delivering their instruction (Abdirasulov, J. 2021; El-Sofany et al.; Basit et al. 2020). As quoted:

"The mode of delivering my instruction is limited face to face. Virtual delivery is impossible due to absence of internet connection in our place." (P6 L 676-677).

Risk-taking

One of the global concern's most recent public health emergencies is the current COVID 19 pandemic. Amid this, education must continue. For the school head, rather situation is precarious that you must consider many things before implementing specific changes. The covid-19 pandemic has grown from a public health crisis to an overarching humanitarian crisis demanding vital social welfare means to mitigate its adverse consequences (Mahapatra et al. 2021; Valikangas et al. 2021; Ancho, I.V, 2020). It supports the statement as quoted:

"It is difficult for us school heads to adjust from our usual practices of delivering our instruction.... many factors must be addressed, including the safety of teachers and other workers." (P6 L 682-684).

Inattentiveness

In far-flung areas, many parents and guardians belong to the Indigenous group of people whose primary way of living is farming. Due to their heavy work, they have no time to get the modules of their children religiously. Also affected by their interest and capability, it worsens their attitude towards modular as curriculum instruction. Parent's psychological distress is a risk factor for developing the externalizing problem in children. The parents neglected the concept and became the worst problem faced by the school. The participants stated that the modules and assessments returned to the teachers have no answers, which will be the basis of computing their grades. Aside from parents' negligence of getting modules, the learners' negative attitude towards modular instruction is considered the main problem encountered by the school head. (Setiawan et al. 2020; Lase et al. 2021; Durisic et al. 2017) (Marchetti et al. 2020; Wendel, M. 2021; Tan et al. 2020). The participant stated that:

"The difficulties they encountered that were referred to me as school head are the following: There are pupils who are enrolled already, but their parents do not get the modules religiously or those who are at risk of dropping out." (P1 L 28-31)

"...but as long goes by only a few of our parents who get and return the modules" (P3 L 303-304)

The second problem we encountered is modules, and assessment does not have answers. (P1 L 32-34)

"Teachers are suffering from late submission of modules or non-submission" (P5. L 561-562)

Uneducated

Parents and guardians in far-flung schools are mostly indigenous people who belong to the low economic status family. Some of them could not send in and experience life in school. Playing their role as teachers to their children is very difficult due to their situation. Parents experiencing high psychological distress may be less attentive to and warm with their children. They may also transfer the burden of their emotional pain to their children, which could affect their children's adjustment (Lase et al. 2021; Stranzl et al. 2021; Tan et al. 2020). In support of this description of how the participants view themselves, the following was quoted:

"The major population of our parents is not well educated, so tough for them to teach their children the things they do not know." (P2 L 171-172)

"The major population of our parents is not well educated, so tough for them to teach their children the things they do not know." (P2 L 163-164).

Burdensome

Aside from the teachers' difficulties in parents' and learners' negative attitudes towards modules, they also suffer from the burden of production of modules. It takes time, even working late into the night, preparing learning materials, giving feedback, and monitoring students' learning process. Teachers work late at night and on weekends to develop learning materials and support their online students—one of the problems raised to the school head during their formal meeting. Even the school head provides all the printing materials, and it is not enough to make the printing job easy due to the many modules to be printed (Lase et al. 2021; Jermittiparsert, K. 2020; Cho et al. 2019). They use the statement to raise the issue:

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

"Also, to my teachers, the complaint raised to me is the condition of the printers. After printing thousands of pages, they experience printing problems like paper jams. Their families also complain about the burden." (P5 L 566-567)

Supervision

All important matters that the school head wants to implement must need close supervision to succeed. It is also necessary for the production and distribution of modules. There must be a strategy in place for how overseeing will be done to minimize or mitigate the problem. It is vital for the school administrator to act and supervise because information obtained from supervisors will be accurate and improve teacher professionalism by maximizing necessary abilities (Susanti et al. 2020; Bafadal et al. 2018; Ebot-Ashu, F. 2019; Mohammed, U.D 2017). As quoted:

"I make certain that all teachers have the materials they need to reproduce the self-learning modules." (P2 L 169-170)

Provision

In this time of the pandemic, MOOE allocation is most on the production of modules. The participant stated that he ensures that all teachers have access to all printing supplies and other requirements for module development. Having a compassionate principal can make all the difference for a teacher. The teacher wants to know that their principal has their best interest in mind. A principal's primary responsibility is to offer continuing collaborative teacher assistance. Mutual trust is the basis of teachers' and principals' relationships (Meador, D. 2017; Uko et al. 2015; Susanti et al. 2020). The following is the participant's response:

"I make certain that all teachers have the materials they need to reproduce the self-learning modules." (P2 L 169-170)

"I ensure that all necessary resources, particularly printers, are available for the printing of modules." (P5 L 572-573)

Raising Fund

Reproduction cost is a big problem to every school in this pandemic, especially those schools where resources are too limited. School administrators must look for a new funding source to meet the demands. Stakeholder participation in corporate processes and practices results in shared benefits. Regarding the relationship of mutual trust between the institution and their stakeholders, the result confirmed a positive and significant relationship with value creation for all groups (de Freitas Langrafe et al. 2020; Ancho, I.V 2020; Uko et al. 2015). As one of the participants stated, it is accurate that she needs to solicit to raise funds for module reproduction.

"...so I solicited bond papers, inks, as well as printers to my former pupils, alumni, and stakeholders". (P4 L 433-434).

Strong Connection

The problem commonly raised regarding modular as curriculum instruction is the parent's and learners' negative behavior towards it. To address the issue, the school principal has made an effort to establish a strong connection and relationship with the parents. It's not just the module problems that can be fixed; it's everything related to them. Students will take their studies more seriously if they know that their professors immerse themselves in their topics and establish high expectations (Mart, C.T 2017; Durisic et al. 2017; Ntekane, A. 2018). At this point, teaching ceases to be a job done by force and turns into an inspiration for students. The participant quoted that:

"I instructed my teachers always to motivate them. Have a home visitation most of our parents are busy in their whole farm day visit the parents in the farm so that the problem is personally referred to them" (P3 L 301-303)

"Before we distribute the modules, we conducted parents' orientation with the help of our sitio officials and PTA." (P5 L 574-575)

"I also conducted limited face to face meetings with parents to disseminate proper distribution and retrieval of modules" (P6 L 704-705).

Transparency

During this pandemic, one of the most expensive things the school needs to allocate a budget is the reproduction of modules. To avoid the rising financial problem, the school must utilize proper use of school MOOE. Aside from that, it is necessary to be open about where the budget will be spent. Transparent internal communication and trust are crucial to

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

uphold employee's willingness to provide resources in the form of job engagement throughout the crisis, when the environment is full of divergent information, adverse reporting, and the risk of becoming infected by a potentially deadly virus (Stranzl et al. 2021; Mohammed et al. 2017; Mohiuddin, Z. 2017; Ancho, I.V, 2020) To provide a statement for this, the participant stated that:

"I make sure that there is enough number of printers, bond papers, ink for the reproduction of modules through proper utilization of MOOE." (P6 701-702).

Teacher-Based Report

Teachers have direct contact with parents, so the school relies on what report the teachers could give through the learners' assessment, class monitoring plan, and monthly monitoring plan. These are the essential tools to assess the need of the learners.

Passionate teachers know that it is their role to encourage active learning and concern themselves with promoting students' intellectual and moral development (Mart, C.T 2017; Bafadal et al. 2018; Whang, N.Y 2021; Solangi, G.M 2017). As participant quoted:

"Through our meetings with the teachers, they are given a time one on one report to the body." (P4 L 438-439)

Close Supervision

Not only must relying on what data the teachers could give, but learners' progress must also closely monitor the school head to know its accuracy. In this way, learners' problems will indeed be addressed. Supervision conducted by the principal can help teachers improve the quality of teaching. As the opinion expressed by several experts, one factor that affects the quality of education is supervision. So, high-quality learning will be obtained if the teachers conduct the supervision function optimally (Susanti et al. 2020; Pramitha, D. 2021; Meador, D. 2017). As quoted by one of the participants:

"Through our meetings with the teachers, they are given a time one on one report to the body." (P4 L 438-439)

"We have a series of formal meetings with my teachers. One of the topics discussed is the progress of the learners." (P5 L 582-583)

Formal and Informal Meetings

The school heads have helped their teachers to improve teaching performance and pupil achievement when they provide feedback and suggestions during supervision and sessions. Teachers and school administrators kept a careful eye on students' development, as did parents' involvement in their children's education. Currently, parents stand as para-teacher to their children. Learners' development and attitude towards their modules mainly depend on the motivation that comes from their parents and guardians. One of the most problematic issues of the school head is following and motivating parents to do their tasks through a regular session with parents. Parental involvement in learning acts as a gel that helps make learning for children pleasant. It encourages them to work even more as they seek to make those closest to them proud Talking to parents and guardians regarding their learners' progress is the best way to address problems. They will understand better the scenario if it is well explained to them (Ntekane, A. 2018; Povey, J.,2016; Page, R. D. 2016). (Guardacasa, et. al 2020; Altun, M. 2017; Noureen, et. al 2020). Participants give the detail of the above statement as quoted:

"We meet parents every end of the month to talk the progress of their children." (P4 L 444-445)

"In our school, most of our parents have no phones for communication.....I need to talk to them face to face." (P5 591-592)

"We conducted orientation of parents by grade level in a limited number only." (P1 L 54-55)

"...conducting limited face to face conference to the parents to discuss learners' progress..." (P6 L 718-719)

"...if found that the child finds difficulties in answering modules, we do intervention through home visitation." (P3 L 317-318).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Build Good Relationship

The school needs respect and sympathy to gain 100% support and participation. Through building friendships and considering them as a big part of schools' development, the school will surely gain their support. The minor formal education institution or unit, the school, is comfortable getting an education and knowledge; if school culture fosters comfort, the learning process is more straightforward (Susanti et al., 2020; Cutler, W. W. 2015; Sanders et al. 2018). It is also brought into account in the study, which represents the school's principal aim and is backed by the following statement:

“ A little friendliness goes a long way, especially in communicating parents.” (P2 L 182-183)

Verbal Appreciation

Employees' work and satisfaction determine the level of progress, their performance, and how productive they would be in their respective jobs. School heads recognize and appreciate to motivate learners and teachers to work hard during this pandemic. It is the way to improve work productivity and maintain excellent performance. The participant stated that one way of providing appreciation is through verbal. The workforce needs to hear positive feedback from their superiors. It was possible to build a positive and harmonious connection (Ndungu, D. 2017; Mari et al. 2021; White, P. 2017). As quoted:

"During meetings, I praised and appreciated teachers who performed well." (P1 L 62-63)

Intangible Rewards

Aside from verbal appreciation, school heads also consider giving teachers and learners intangible rewards such as certificates to recognize their excellent works. This award was given to students who got an average grade of 90. Employees equally rewarded are more committed to the firm and hence work harder and smarter to achieve the company's objectives (Sitek et al. 2018; Yoon et al. 2015; Schweyer et al. 2018). The participants quoted that they awarded this by a quarter within a year.

"And for the parents and learners, I give my praise and recognition by giving certificates to those learners with satisfactory grades. (P3 L 327-328"

“.....For the parents who become a part of a very crucial part in the learning so little recognition by giving a certificate of appreciation.” (P4 6-470)

"Every recognition Day, all teachers who performed well will be given certificate of recognition /commendation and reward." (P6 L 724-725)

Giving Sympathy

The connection between a teacher and principal should be powerful enough to bring any problem or issue and trust that they will. One way of appreciation made by my participants is to listen and give sympathy to their teachers. It is an intense kind of appreciation but so meaningful, and it is a feeling of positivity that may affect everybody's feelings. It will help build a solid and intimate relationship with the boss and the workers (Spehar et al. 2016; Jena et al. 2018; Randel et al. 2018).

".....ask them their ideas and then listen to them, share their success outside the school, leave them notes and help them learn, develop and grow". (P2 L 190-191)

“We have been past blessed to have some fantastic teachers. My purpose is to make all of the teachers and staff in the group adopted. Remind the teachers and families that they're not alone.” (P4 452-454)

"I always give my sympathy to my teachers, especially now that the burden of reproduction is in their hands." (P5 L 597-598)

Difficult

We believe that today's situations are unique and significant though they adapted in their day-to-day experience as a school leader. But school leaders must be committed and competent to deliver the purpose of Basic education. According

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

to the participants, school leadership in this new normal is more complex than in previous years. Leadership development is often discussed in the context of leadership coaching and consulting. It is critical for succession planning and organizational success, but it is also essential for crisis preparedness. There are numerous avenues to develop leaders, but there is no "magic box" of tools and methods for effective leadership development, especially considering leaders in different organizations with different needs (Shufutinsky et al. 2020; Bozkurt et al. 2020; Tus, J. (2021). In detail, the following are the participant statements:

“Instructional leadership in new normal is difficult but in one way to capacitate and improve yourself as a leader.” (P1 L 72-73)

“In this time of the pandemic, it is tough to impose any of my instructions. (P4 L 475-476)

“...we do all possible ways to be an effective leader. All the means and strategies are applied even though it is very hard, especially communication.” (P5 L 607-608)

“Instructional leadership in the new normal is quite tricky and challenging....many things to be considered...following some protocol....online submission of reports...” (P6 L 735-737)

Challenging

Due to pandemics, sudden changes happen in all aspects, especially education. In some way, no one was spared from the impacts of these transformations. Changes affected school leaders, and they had to discard old methods and embrace new ones. The participants also described new typical leadership as challenging since everything changes and no option but to take all of it to continue education. A significant difference between then and now is that there was no possibility of moving education online, even in the current era. ADIGÜZEL, et. al 2020; Butron, P. V 2021; Ancheta, et. al 2020). To support the detail, the participants quoted:

“Instructional leadership in the new normal is very challenging. For me, modular as curriculum instruction is not effective in the school where I am assigned, but I have no option but to follow what is ordered.” (P3 L333-337)

“The COVID-19 pandemic has raised many challenging to our educational system. Yet, it also presents an opportunity to reconsider the delivery of education”(P2 L 196-197)

“...need to be resilient and proactive in all endeavors to achieve a common goal” P1 L 26-2

Table 2: Thematic Analysis of the Impact of changes to the Instructional Leadership of the participants.

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
A. Ways to reinforce instructional issues 1. They are giving teachers the technical assistance they need. 2. They are talking to teachers one on one to know their problems. 3. We are encouraging them to work better. 4. Always remind teachers of their oath. 5. Applied discipline if necessary. 6. Do not allow them to take personal business if they have an unfinished task.	1. Giving technical assistance 2. Excellent listener 3. Fair and consistent
B. Teachers' Reaction 7. They applied what was suggested. 8. They positively take my advice. 9. Always their sympathy. 10. They are respectful in following my instruction. 11. Some teachers follow with hesitation. 12. Some teachers are eager but hesitant to follow.	4. Submissive 5. Hesitated
C. Way of Assisting Teachers in Professional Growth 13. Encouraged teachers to attend training and seminars. 14. Encourage them to join online training. 15. Encourage them to pursue their master's degrees. 16. Constant follow up and post-conference	6. Encouragement 7. Post-conference/Follow up

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

D. Factors Affecting Conduct of Seminars 17. Did not conduct due to no internet connections 18. Conducted due to few 19. Due to module replication, there is a financial constraint.	8. Inaccessibility 9. Manageable 10. Inadequate resources
E. Developed Follow Up Plans 20. To conduct regular SLAC session 21. To conduct regular inset for teachers. 22. Conduct lesson observation religiously.	11. Faculty Development 12. Lesson observation
F. About Being a School Head 23. They were dealing strictly with administrative duties. 24. They are focused on what they are tasked to do. 25. We are seeking the good of everybody. 26. I know how to handle small to big things. 27. We are considering problems as a lesson learned. 28. Facing problem help me to be responsible. 29. Solving circumstances makes me stronger and wiser. 30. Experience as a classroom teacher helps me to perform well.	13. Deeply Committed 14. Realization
G. View about Instructional Leadership in New Normal 31. Develop the courage to motivate others. 32. Reflect on the importance of shared vision. 33. Provide my teachers with the right goal to follow. 34. You are a good model. 35. To serve my school and to be their role model. 36. Effective and be responsive in all my action	15. Inspiring others 16. Provide Support and Vision 17. Effective Role Model

Giving Technical Assistance

A lot of conflict arises in a school situation, which sometimes includes teachers as the cause. And it is very favorable when the school head takes it positively and with sensitivity, like giving technical assistance rather than criticism on the person involved. When teachers develop their teaching profession, they can influence student accomplishment. Teachers with a high level of commitment also motivates students to involve in school activities (Altun M. 2017; Maggin et al. 2015; Maag, J. 2016). This situation reflected on one of the participants' responses and quoted like this:

“I reinforce teachers with difficulties in following instructional issues by giving the technical assistance guiding them on what they need to improve for the good of instruction” (P1 L 82-83)

“...I am always with them to give technical assistance and to guide them every time they need” (P6 L 747-748)

“...build resilience to overcome the challenge of new normal, also giving technical assistance” (P2 L 206-207)

Excellent Listener

Giving technical assistance and being a good listener is the best way to reinforce teachers with instructional issues. To listen to them means also taking the burden they have. The more effective the communication within the group and the more influential the group performs as an integrated part toward attaining corporate goals and objectives. Many problems arise in school due to loss of communication or miscommunications ((Mohiuddin, Z. A. 2017; Bushardt et al. 2018; Itzchakov et al. 2018). The participants stated that:

“There are some instances that one of my teachers reacted due to the overload paper works, but I handle it subtly.....talk to him in the office to solve the problem” (P3 L 346-348)

Fair and Reliable

When it comes to student discipline or parent settings, teachers despise it when principals contradict themselves. When making decisions, a principal should always be fair and consistent. Even school heads consider their teachers as critical human resources in school, but there is also the time that the school head will decide firmly as the situation requires. To be a leader means taking the risk of whatever big and small things you choose and, of course, to be fair and consistent to your words and leading to what is suitable for many, not for one ((Meador, D. 2017; Ferrell, R. S. 2016; Olanrewaju et al. 2019). As quoted from the participant's response, the following statement was viewed:

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

“Beforehand, I always remind them of their oath as teachers. I also applied discipline to them if necessary, and the example is I did not allow them to go to take their business if they have unfinished task” (P5 L 616-617)

“... what is required is a proactive, inclusive and transparent approach that does not downplay information” (P4 L 491-492)

Submissive

Being subservient to the professors is one of the reactions identified from the methods outlined above for resolving instructional challenges. They follow orders because they feel it is the proper course of action. Teachers who are dedicated to their job seek opportunities for professional development regularly. Instructors committed to their profession are considered to work with other teachers to help their pupils learn. Most of the time, by applying positive discipline by leaders, it also gains positive responses from subordinates, like being respectful and obedient, as shown in the result of the study. Academic oversight of school principals is one way to improve teaching quality. The existence of a leader in the education unit is supposed to aid instructors in carrying out their responsibilities professionally (Susanti et al. 2020; Kearney et al. 2016; Muteswa, R. (2016) (Altun, M. 2017; Junker et al. 2016; Krishnakumar et al. 2015). Most of the time, by applying positive discipline by leaders, it also gains positive responses from subordinates, like being respectful and obedient, as shown in the result of the study. Academic supervision of school principals is an effort that can be done to optimize the quality of teaching. A leader in the education division is expected to assist teachers in carrying out their duties professionally (Susanti et al., 2020; Kearney et al., 2016; Muteswa, R. (2016). It is reflected in the participants' view that most of her teachers' responses are all positive. As quoted:

“Since the teachers are the front liners in education must continue, most of them respond differently, some were so eager, and yet others were hesitant due to pandemic.” (P4 L 495-496)

Hesitated

Due to the recent pandemic and overload of paper works, some teachers are hesitant to follow what is ordered by their school head. Some teachers are bothered about coping with their work over their safety. Teachers who do not use the new media platform are given more obligations. Teachers who go above and beyond the call of duty are the only ones who can bring about these improvements. (Ebot-Ashu, F. 2019; Herath et al. 2020; Legaspi et al. 2020). To quote this, this is the participant's view:

“Based on my observation, I am happy because they applied what I've suggested to them...” (P1 L 87-88)

“.....They always take my advises and suggestions positively and respond to changes as what is good for the learners.” (P2 L 212-213)

“... If they see and understand that my action is for the good of the school. I always gain their sympathy”. (P5 L 621-622)

“Based on my experience as an instructional leader, teachers were very submissive.” (P6 L 751-752)

“My teachers are so respectful when it comes to following my instruction” (P3 L 351-352)

“For me maybe respect is the most important for them to follow orders as they showed to me” (P5 L 622-623)

Encouragement

Self-esteem is one of the pieces of evidence of professional development. Encouragement is the key to booster self-esteem. It is the healthiest motivator. When refueled by encouragement, we feel the confidence and support others have in us. School heads consider encouragement as one of the tools to push teachers' personal development. Supportive colleagues are also another factor that is positively related to job satisfaction. Due to the considerable amount of time the employees spend, their colleagues are part of their everyday lives. Friendly and supportive co-workers can increase an employee's job satisfaction (Wu et al., 2017; Zubair et al., 2015; Daresh et al., 2015). It was demonstrated in the following statement:

“I assist teachers in their personal development in this new normal setting by encouraging them to attend more seminars and pieces of training or enroll in online classes” (P1 L 94-96)

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

“I need to show my help to my teachers but be firm in implementing the orders at the same time. I consider their weaknesses and help them work it through conferences. (P2 L 219-221)

“Most of my teachers were not courageous....but through the days they able to adapt, adjust and improve because of my encouragement” (P4 L 504-505)

“I encourage the teachers to attend online seminars/training or even enrolled in online class” (P6 L 758-759)

“There are some opportunities offered to us by Deped, and I encourage them to join.” (P5 L 627-628)

Post Conference/Follow Up

In every school, there are ways in how teachers' preparedness in terms of curriculum instruction and professional development is measured. Series of classroom observation and monitoring by walking. One of the participants that he takes this to measure teachers' readiness. After that, he conducted a post-conference to discuss the teacher's concerns and a close follow-up to know the teachers' needs. Supervision conducted by the principal can help teachers improve the quality of teaching in the classroom. It is the one factor that affects the quality of teaching. Teachers who perform the supervisory duty well will provide high-quality learning (Susanti et al. 2020; Hilton et al. 2015; Peters et al. 2015). The following individuals' perspectives are provided to supplement the detail:

“Through the result of CO and MBWA, I already determine the need of improvement of my teachers, a simple post-conference and a follow up from me will do.” (P3 L 35-359)

Inaccessibility

Newer mobile technologies provide opportunities to communicate faster and create new social practices and communication patterns. While practically everyone has access to the internet, specific schools and communities do not. Some of the schools are situated on the study's premises. Inaccessibility to the internet is one of the reasons mentioned by the participant in conducting seminars and training at the school level (Adnan et al. 2020; Palvia et al. 2018; Rasheed et al. 2020). As quoted:

“We were not able to conduct seminars and training in this new normal setting....location of our school is not accessible to any internet connections to this virtual training” (P1 L 100-101)

“In school, we did not conduct our seminars. I encourage them to attend webinar held by central office... I allow them to stay at Kablon ES... where internet access is available” (P3 L 368-2370)

Manageable

The existence of teams in school units plays a significant role. It positively correlates with the synergy among school community members, team motivation, and educational operation. Each member plays an essential role in the organization's success. In other cases, belonging to a small group unit becomes a strength. Even in this pandemic were gathering strictly follows health protocol, and a large number is prohibited, being in a small group is advantageous. As mandated, every event held in school should apply social distancing and health protocol. Seminars and training are also advised to conduct virtual or proper social distancing. Having few members in one school is advantageous in training seminars approved by the Division Office (Mulang, A. 2015; Avidov-Ungar, O. 2016; Patton et al. 2015). Two of our participants responded that this statement is true. As quoted:

“Yes, we conduct seminar and workshop.....we do it through limited face to face, and it is easy to handle since we are few only” (P4 L 514-516)

“Yes, we conduct seminars/workshop in our school....it was approved due to our few numbers” (P6 L 767-768)

“We did not conduct seminars and workshops.....we maximized our funds to production of modules”. (P2 L 232-233)

"The sole lecture that we had at our school was for teachers and parents to learn about the modules."As of now, we have not enough budget for internet access and other expenses” (P5 L 637-639)

Inadequate Resources

Conducting seminars and training also required enough budget for expenses. Due to limited resources during this pandemic, some of the school head priorities other essential things than training and seminars like purchasing printing materials and others. Two participants share their feelings about how the inadequacy of resources affects the conduct of workshops and training at the school level (Whitworth et al. 2015; Körkkö et al. 2016; Kennedy, M. M. 2016) To quote their statements:

"The sole lecture that we had at our school was for teachers and parents to learn about the modules."As of now, we have not enough budget for internet access and other expenses" (P5 L 637-639)

" We were not able to conduct seminars and training in this new normal setting....location of our school is not accessible to any internet connections to this virtual training" (P1 L 100-101)

Faculty Development

Seminars, workshops, and insets provide a chance to interact with experts from a specific field. Teachers tend to learn about the latest information in the teaching and learning process and other related issues and concerns by discussing the relevant topics of particular subjects. All teachers are required to participate in professional development. However, teachers want those professional development opportunities to apply to their situation. These are why school heads prioritized seminars and workshops as their plans to follow up teachers' development (Jolles, R. L. 2017; Essien et al. 2016; Avidov-Ungar, O. 2016). Most of the participants have responded to this. As quoted:

"...my next plan for growth is to conduct a series of seminars and workshops funded by MOOE." (P3 L 378-79)

"...I plan to conduct INSET to help the teachers improve their professional growth." (P6 L 774-775)

"I plan to encourage my teachers to attend virtual/ online seminars and training that able them to develop professional growth and development." (P3 L 521-522)

Learners Development

Many of my participants saw seminars and workshops as the areas in which they wanted to concentrate their efforts. But there is one response that focuses more on pupils' development due to teachers' manifestation. Conducting classroom observation is one of the most effective ways of close supervision. Because the information gathered from supervisors will be accurate and can be utilized as a guide to developing teacher professionalism by maximizing the talents that must be acquired, school principals must act and oversee (Meador, D. 2017; Ampofo et al., 2019; Ngole et al. 2021). One participant stated that she would be focusing on the students' success. The following was cited:

"...I encourage them to share their expertise by conducting SLAC to fellow teachers to help one another" (P1 L 111-112)

"...my next plan for growth is to conduct a series of seminars and workshops funded by MOOE." (P3 L 378-79)

"I conducted follow up on their achievements, training, and assessments. I also looked upon their E-SAT. After that, I prepare and allocate budget for their seminars and training." (P5 L 644-646)

"...I plan to conduct INSET to help the teachers improve their professional growth." (P6 L 774-775)

"I plan to encourage my teachers to attend virtual/ online seminars and training that able them to develop professional growth and development." (P3 L 521-522)

"I planned to conduct lesson observation strictly and religiously, in this time I strictly check the assessments released to the pupils if it is suited to their capacity." (P2 L 240-242)

Deeply Committed

Great teachers will attend and work when the school head has a good, committed principal. They work hard, grow, and ultimately impact the student's growth. Upon reaching years being a school head, some experiences define how effective the leadership style applied in every school. Two participants responded that their career stage as school heads helps them be deeply committed to their profession. It also helps them deal with administrative and instructional duties that molded them to be effective (Bafadal et al. 2018; Ferrell, R. S. 2016; Peters et al. 2018).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Amid crisis, leadership needs to go beyond the edge of chaos and adaptive and situational leadership to an amplified, more advanced level, potentially embroiled in a continual state of chaotic nonlinear change. Being a leader is a significant job. It needs to take selfishness to be effective. It also has various responsibilities, and the most important is managing human resources. School administrators are expected to be more flexible in using school resources during this pandemic. Due to this function, two of the participants viewed that their function as a leader helps them be more responsible, looking up to everybody's welfare as their priority than themselves (Ngole et al. 2021; Rehman et al. 2019; Kolodziejczyk, J. 2015). The following views support the above statement:

"I'm new in this field, but I never hesitate to continue to learn, innovate and adapt all changes needed for me to grow in this role because it was trusted to me; therefore, I need to give my 100% efforts to my service." (P1 L 117-119)

"Being school head, I spend the majority of my time dealing strictly with administrative duties and an instructional leader who is charged with redefining role to become the primary learner in the community." (P2 L 247-249)

"Being school head is not easy for me since many people depend on my decision." (P4 L 528-529)

"So far, I'm so blessed for given an opportunity as school head. As for me, God gave me this role to help the community." (P5 L 650-651)

Being school head is not easy for me since many people depend on my decision." (P4 L 528-529)

"So far, I'm so blessed for given an opportunity as school head. As for me, God gave me this role to help the community." (P5 L 650-651)

Realization

Aside from the prime duty of teaching and learning, school heads are responsible for management functions such as scheduling, reporting, handling relation with parents and the community, and dealing with the multiple crises and unique situations that inventible in schools. During this pandemic, school heads have been under enormous pressure to put together the responses needed regarding the importance of education. The participant reflected that he learned when dealing with instructional issues and other concerns. Leaders need to be educated about and gain experience in various leadership styles to adopt those styles when the situational needs crisis agilely. A School head who spends more time as a classroom teacher is likely to be an advantage in dealing with teachers' behavior issues. He can easily understand the burden of being in the classroom to handle it (Aureada, J. 2020; Meador, D. 2017; Mohiuddin, Z.A 2017) Shufutinsky et al. 2020; Whang, N.Y 2021; Susanti et al. 2020).

To support these themes, the following is the response of the participant.

"Facing a lot of problems and issues in school, help me to become a responsible leader. It help me how to handle every situation fair to everybody" (P3 L 386-387)

" My experience being a classroom teacher before I designated as school head help me to become able to do the task being a school head." (P6 L 779-780)

Inspiring Others

Leaders who maintain a harmonious working relationship with workers will positively impact their performance, and influential leaders always get the best out of their workers' performance. Several views state the role of school head to the school management but two of the participants quoted as inspiring others. An inspirational leader does not tell about his commitment but shows it in his behavior and actions. It also demonstrates a solid commitment to the organization's mission and vision. Shared passion makes the school soar in the accomplishment of its mission and vision (Mohammed et al. 2017; Solangi, G.M 2017; Meador, D. 2017)

Provide Support and Vision

Providing a vision for the entire school is the single most crucial role of the practice as a leader. Teachers and parents cannot be expected to participate in a joint effort if they don't know the practice's goals. It is also necessary that the leader provide all the resources needed to achieve the target goal. Employees love to work when all essential resources are well equipped. School heads have various responsibilities, including human resources, financial resources, educational activities with students and teachers, and more. School heads are expected to be more flexible in managing school

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

resources to keep changing guidelines and circumstances (Whang, N.Y 2021; Mahapatra et al. 2021; Ancho, I.V 2020). Two of the participants responded that their role as school heads focuses on providing support to their teachers and others working in the school.

“Instructional leadership in the new normal is very challenging. I continue to aspire for more, for myself development so that I can inspire my fellow workers to do things differently...”(P1 L 126-128)

“... I want to devote more of my time to my function to be more effective. I want to inspire more people...”(P6 L 792-793)

Effective Role Model

Leadership is, therefore, essential to the survival and effectiveness of organizational performance. As the organization grows and expectations about its performance increase, demand for good leadership tends to multiply. They were a school head demonstrates how to lead than to manage. It empowers through desired behavior and avoids inconsistencies in giving services ((Mohammed et al. 2017; Bafadal et al. 2018; Guardacasa et al. 2020; Susanti et al. 2020). Two of my participants gave their point of view as their leadership described as an effective role model.

“But as long as I can, I exerted all my effort to provide all the assistance my teachers need.” (P2 L 259-260)

“ I always explain to my teachers that we need and we should follow orders from higher-ups even we find it difficult. I always reflect on myself that we are not the one that is affected but everybody. If we often complain, we achieve nothing but heartaches” (P5 L 660-664)

“...Even though there are so many issues that need my concern, but I tried to be a good model to them, serving unselfishly.” (P3 L 396-397)

“This time of the pandemic, the devotion of my function was measured. All decision I exerted brings effect to the people surround me.” (P4 L 534-536)

4. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the crucial findings with limitations, implications, and significance of existing studies. This study sought to understand better the instruction leadership of elementary school heads in this new normal. I hope to have an in-depth understanding of how the school leads in this pandemic time.

Major Findings

The case study research revealed significant themes in the participants' views on delivering instruction. As a school head, providing their education is through a situational and optional approach that uses face-to-face and sometimes uses different media types depending on the situation. Another stated that obedience to the law is essential for instruction. The school's actions should follow IATF and DepEd guidelines. Due to the absence of internet connections and other mobile applications, other participants have no option but to deliver their instruction face-to-face or on the traditional way of providing instruction.

Based on the participants' experiences observation, they gave various problems they met in delivering their instruction. These are mindfulness, limited or no access to the internet, lack of communication gadgets, and risk-taking. While one participant responded to it possibly and favorably as handling in few teachers means no problem in communication.

Problems and solutions were stressed in the implementation of modular as curriculum education. Most of the problem arises from parents' inattention about modules' importance and poor educational background. The negative behavior of learners such as laziness and tardiness of getting and returning modules were also noted, also burdensome of teachers in production of modules.

In terms of monitoring learners' progress, teachers verify reports such as a result of assessments, class monitoring plan, and monthly monitoring plan and through close supervision of school head to the learners. And about parents' participation is monitored through the regular session, building good relationships, and formal and informal meetings.

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Teachers, parents, and students who did well after being observed were rewarded verbally with intangible benefits and sympathy. The participants described leadership in this pandemic time as challenging due to the uncertainty of the situation. It is difficult because many changes come up every day. It is challenging because you need to face changes every day.

Given participants on ways to reinforce teachers dealing with instructional issues, the responses are assisting them to be an excellent listener and fair and consistent. Most of the teachers reacted to the techniques positively, and they were submissive, respectful, and obedient. But some teachers also got hesitated to follow due to the heavy workload.

Participants also claimed that they encourage teachers to attend online seminars and workshops and post-conference and follow-up to assist teachers' development. But there are reasons listed as factors on conducting seminars and workshops for teachers' development, such as inaccessibility and inadequate resources. One of the participants viewed that he had no difficulties conducting any seminars and workshops due to their few numbers in school.

To view their experience preparing them for instructional leadership, the participants responded that their role helps them become more committed and responsible. They learned from the problems met. And they learned through experiences. The participants also viewed how they analyzed their role as an instructional leader in this new normal as inspiring other, providing support and vision, and being an effective role model.

Comparison of Findings with Existing Literature

Ways of School Head in Delivering Instruction

After gathering the participants' responses, the following are the ways of different elementary school heads assigned in far-flung areas to deliver their daily instruction upon the changes made in the new typical setting.

Situational and Optional

The participants' responses were similar to what Francisco et al. (2020) cited. They were encouraged to become more digital, especially communicating with their professors, pupils, co-workers, etc. It is as if they shifted from the traditional style into something more adaptive to changes that the world dictates nowadays. Practical school head must adopt what the situation needed (Ancho, I.V 2020; Bafadal et al. 2018)

Obedience

As IATF mandated, it is essential to consider every individual's health in every situation. It gave an additional burden to every school head on how it could be possible without risking anybody. The school must provide solutions to pressing issues towards actions. School heads overcome challenges by being active problem-solvers, initiative-drivers, and bold to do the heavy lifting (Fiarman, S. 2017; Colbert et al. 2016; Cho et al. 2019).

Traditional

The current pandemic situation reveals that not all schools are ready to adopt the changes. Call or a higher preparedness depending on the situational and contextual circumstances we find ourselves in to accelerate fine-tuning, various modalities suitable to experiences, conditions, and perspective. It is not the issue of availability of access to the internet or other media but the willingness to transport information and instruction in any means (Guardacasa et al. 2020).

Problems Met in Delivering Instruction

Due to the location of schools where the participants were assigned, they noted the problems met in delivering their instruction as follow:

Manageable

In this new situation, school management plays a vital role in teachers' performance in school. When teachers see that their leadership has improved something they care about, it brings satisfaction that fuels them to continue. It is advantageous for her to handle and lead her school in participants' responses due to their few numbers. Even internet access is absent in their location, and they can still have their regular meetings following the guidelines and protocols set by the Department of Education (Fiarman, S. 2017; Basit et al. 2020)

Mindfulness

The current health issues bring a lot of changes to school leadership, particularly in instructional matters. The current situation calls to be critical on how the school leaders see the coming days and visualize the future. It is also the time to consider many things such as "preparing, sense-making, decision-making, and meaning-making, terminating and learning (Ancho, I.V 2020; Basit et al. 2020).

No Internet Access

One of the most affected areas of school leadership is communication. It is vital in an organization since, when properly utilized, it can lead to successful and effective leadership. Today's focus of school heads must not only of digital transformation and digitalization but also that school leaders must be strategic and flexible in this extraordinary situation (Herath et al. 2020; Francisco et al. 2020; Kegeyan, S. E. 2016).

Lack of Gadget

Several studies proved that gadgets have a significant contribution to improving communication, and their absence may cause problems in the effective delivery of communication. In this new standard-setting, the importance of media and gadgets in touch is vital and may cause issues in its absence. Participants responded that one of the problems they met during the new normal is the lack of devices of parents and pupils that causes a delay in transmitting information which was previously discussed as the leading role of devices (Cho et al. 2019; Kegeyan, S. E. (2016). Verhagen, et al. 2020)

Risk-Taking

One of the participants shared that instructional leadership in the new standard is a very risk-taking job since there are many things to be considered, especially the health of his staff. Principals have a significant role in dealing with the challenges in the new normal. Therefore, the principal must have a strategic approach to improving the quality of education in a unique setting without compromising all safety. Implementing school activities in this new typical setting is very risky considering every individual's health in an organization. (Harris, et. al 2020; Basit, et. al 2020; Netolicky, D. M. 2020).

Problems Encountered in the Implementation of Self-Learning Module as Curriculum Instruction

As the schools in Tupi South District implemented the Self-Learning Modules as curriculum instruction, the following are the responses to the problems encountered during the implementation.

Inattentiveness

Pupils' teaching and facilitation of learning were passed on to parents in the new environment. Effective parent-child communication will result in a positive outlook in school and better skills attainment. Parents assume the burden of parenting and facilitating learning to provide safety and a healthy environment. Involvement begins inside their homes, where a constructive attitude towards learning is displayed. Parents need to understand their unique roles to guide their children fully thoroughly. When parents do not fully understand these matters, their child's academic achievement will also be significantly affected (Samoy et al. 2021; Boonk et al. 2018; Castro et al., 2015)

One participant exclaimed that learners' negative attitude towards answering modules is her main problem in this new normal. Thus, considering this as the result of parents' negligence towards their children's educational perspective. The positive effect of parental involvement in education the non-academic thing is that children are easier to pass the transition to new schools, increase the presence of children in school, and children have better behavior and can reduce children's bad behavior. Parents have different contributions in educating their children. Therefore, parental involvement in early childhood education is the participation of parents in the education of their children, whether in the home in the form of parenting, discussing with children, and support of home and learning relating to communication with the school, parental participation in school activities, and joining the parents' community (Setiawan et al. 2020; Castro et al. 2015; Muller et al. 2018)

Uneducated

Parents played a vital role as teachers to their children in this new standard-setting. On the other hand, parents can teach their children their modular courses if they are equally knowledgeable. These concerns arose as the problem when one participant responded that the low educational background of their parents affected the achievement of the learners. Like a real teacher in the usual residential teaching and learning, parents in the new normal impinge different beliefs on their ability, attitude, and disposition while facilitating their children in their learning tasks. However, they need to understand that teaching is a vital and diverse task requiring introspection to design an effective learning climate. (Samoy, et. al 2021; Boonk, et. al 2018; Castro, et. al 2015).

Burdensome

During this new standard-setting, the problem regarding students learning was closely focused on the parents and learners and some teachers' burdensome coping with their job, especially in printing modules. One participant pondered on the instructors' load in terms of working circumstances. This result was closely tied to R. J. Collie's (2021) research. He listed the many problems and obligations that instructors face due to the abrupt changes in the educational system. Somatic burden, stress related to change, and emotional exhaustion are three work-related outcomes that provide understanding about teachers' functioning (Berwick, D. M. 2020;)

Ways of Overcoming Difficulties

On the responses to the problems encountered during the implementation of the Self-Learning module as curriculum instruction, the following are the responses on how they overcame the said difficulties.

Supervision

As enumerated the new standard's problems and challenges, school heads' ability to regulate school issues played a vital role. One of the primary functions of the school head is to supervise. In this setting where everything is uncertain, close supervision is badly needed to apply abrupt changes if the option taken was not applicable. Susanti et al. (2020) stressed the necessity of school principals acting and supervising because information acquired from supervisors will be accurate and can be utilized to adopt ways to increase teacher professionalism by optimizing the abilities that must be had (Saleh et al. 2019; Agih, A. A. 2015)

Provision

As the result of close supervision, the school can determine all necessary things the school needed, and the next step is to provide it. According to Solangi, G. M. (2017), teachers' job satisfaction can result from having a supportive school head. It can significantly influence staff attitude and how the school functions with teachers' attitude and behavior. The significance of school principal motivation for job satisfaction is also emphasized. Its goal is to investigate the role of principals in addressing issues concerning teachers' job satisfaction and motivation (Peters, R. S. 2015; Hutton, D. M. 2017; Mulcahy, D. E. 2019)

Raising Funds

It is the essential responsibility of the school head to facilitate school resources to provide what the school needs. During the reproduction of modules, one of the teachers' concerns is the shortage of supply for production. As stated in the result, the school communicated with stakeholders to address other school needs. The relationship of mutual trust between the institutions and stakeholders gained a positive outlook (de Freitas Langrafe et al. 2020; Ntekane, A. 2018).

Strong Communication

Commonly, the problem arises in an organization due to a lack of proper communication. It hinders the progress and involvement of everyone. To avoid and overcome difficulties brought by this new normal, the participants stated that having strong communication within the group is very important. Substantial communication help works engagement be more active and participative. It bridges the gap that may result in misunderstanding and chaos (Ter Hoeven et al., 2020; Kegeyan, S. E. 2016; Spehar et al., 2016)

Transparency

Pandemic brought many related changes that caused anxiety and stress to every individual. The school head's role is to supervise and impose strategies to lessen the said burdens. Transparent in every aspect of management encouraged employees to work and perform better. To minimize the potential loss of attentive and absorbed individuals, organizations should strengthen the efforts to meet employees' needs during the crisis, which is possible through a transparent approach (Stranzl et al. 2020; Faubert, B. C. 2019; Vaillant, D. 2015)

Monitoring Learners' Progress

The following are how the participants monitor their learners' progress during the implementation of Self-Learning modules as curriculum instruction.

Teacher-Based Reports

One of the functions and responsibilities of teachers is to follow up on learners' achievements to address their needs. Since the teachers are the ones who have direct contact with the learners, the school head reached the concern of teachers to follow up on the status of the learners. Passionate teachers know the importance of interaction between teachers, teacher-student relationships, and the quality of teachers' work at school. (Mart, C. 2017; Giroux, H. A. 2018; Mart, C. T 2017)

Close-Supervision

The teachers facilitate students' achievement, and the school head to not rely only on the data gathered by teachers. According to the study of Susanti et al. (2020), supervision of school heads to teachers' performance increased the quality of learning and ended in quality of education. Management carried out in schools, especially those carried out by principals on academic aspects, is a form of responsibility of a school principal to improve the quality of learning. Academic supervision must become a culture in schools so that the implementation of management can continue to be carried out sustainably without any party feeling aggrieved or oppressed by the existence of academic supervision Mart, C. T 2020; Meador, D. 2017; Mohiuddin; Z. A 2017).

Monitoring Parents' Participation

To improve the participation of learners in the new curriculum implementation, participants also monitored the participation of parents as the para teacher of learners as follows:

Formal and Informal Meetings

As many studies showed, supportive parents' learning is well-motivated. This concept is essential in a new typical setting. Parents stand as the teacher of their children, and the teachers are only to follow up. Students need a positive learning experience to succeed in school: providing support, motivation, and quality instruction. With the increasing demands on the family, parental consent in the education of students extends beyond the school building (Đurišić et al., 2017). The school head must allocate enough time to meet parents and talk about their experiences in answering the modules. As stated by one participant, it is her way to follow up the participation of their parents (Page, R.D 2016; Setiawan et al. 2020; Sanders et al. 2018)

There are many motivations for parents not to be involved in school concerns is the fact that schools sometimes fail to create strong links between homes and schools or an environment where parents do not feel welcomed in schools, especially low-income earners. They felt separated from bars among others and refused to get involved. To bring the barriers, the school head and teachers must conduct formal and informal meetings to think they belong to school decision-making (Lase et al. 2021; Fairman et al. 2015; Bafadal et al. 2018).

Build Good Relationship with Parents

Parenting, for many, is the most critical and challenging job ever to have and a role that gets little recognition. Today, it is essential due to the challenges they need to overcome in their child's learning and development. According to Ntekane A. (2018), parental involvement in education acts as a gel that helps to make learning for children pleasant and encourages them to work even more as they seek to make those closest to them proud. This new normal, it is necessary to follow parents' participation toward Self-Learning Modules as curriculum instruction. As the participants responded, they conducted the regular session, built a good relationship with parents, and conducted the formal and informal meetings (Wendel, M. 2021; Cutler, W.W 2015; Boonk et al. 2018)

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

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Giving of Praise and Appreciation

To improve the performance of every individual, the participants responded on how they give their praises and appreciation to the teachers, parents, and learners.

Verbal Appreciation

From the participants' view, they give appreciation and recognition to their teachers, parents, and learners who perform well as motivated and doing excellent. It does not only highlight the importance of employee recognition, but it also outlines one of our basic needs as an employee and human beings. The impact of giving appreciation to the employees to their performance. It is essential also that the employees hear positive feedbacks every time to encourage satisfaction on the job and also to feel the spirit of belongingness (Ndungu, D. N. 2017; Channar et al. 2017, Ngwa et al. 2019)

Intangible Rewards

The participants responded that they consistently award certificates of recognition and medals to students with excellent performance to motivate performance. Giving intangible rewards increase the motivation in terms of individuals' performance. And the highly motivated one will work well and put more endeavor to achieve the goal (Channar et al. 2017; Saqib et al. 2015; Yoon et al. 2015)

Giving Sympathy

If the relationship between the school head and teachers was very established, it is strong enough to resolve issues and not reach a vulnerable stage efficiently. The pressure of a new typical setting added a burden to teachers, especially those assigned in far-flung areas. With the help, the school head will show sympathy and motivation to the teachers. The participant reflected that it is essential for him to listen to the teachers to understand them. In his study, Martono et al. (2018) also emphasized the positive effect of motivation on the satisfaction of every employee. Remuneration and job satisfaction are two significant factors in individual performance improvement. In addition, remuneration can improve motivation and job satisfaction (Randel et al. 2018; Spehar et al. 2016)

View as Instructional Leadership Described

The following is how the participants responded to how their instructional leadership is described in this new typical scenario:

Difficult

The current challenges in health issues bring sudden changes to school management. It resulted in the overwhelming number of concerns that bothered the time of the school head. As the participant responded, leading the school in this new typical setting is a big difference compared to the normal one. It reflects the situation's complexities and the institution's leadership (Shufutinsky et al. 2020; Tus, J. 2021; Whang, N.Y 2021).

Challenging

Leading is complex since many decisions and consequences depend on acting and reacting. According to ADIGÜZEL et al. (2020), it was emphasized the different factors affecting employees' performance that must consider by every leader. It is also essential to reconsider every matter that made the leadership challenge, as noted in the participants' responses.

Ways to Reinforce Instructional Issues

In delivering their instruction, participants faced different reactions from their staff. The following are how they responded to the instructional issues they faced.

Giving Technical Assistance

There are cases where teachers need to receive technical assistance from the school head rather than criticism. In some issues raised, some cases involving teachers are the cause. The participants' perspective of providing technical service rather than criticism was emphasized to deal with this. Committed teachers always seek continuous professional development. It is believed that teachers who commit to their professional work collaboratively with other teachers to nurture the learning of the students (Altun, M. 2017; Wu et al. 2017; Tria, J.Z 2020).

Excellent Listener

One participant responded that in helping teachers resolve instructional issues, it is necessary to listen to them and allocate enough time. An effective school leader is an exceptional listener. A leader has an open-door policy. They do not dismiss anyone who feels they need to talk to them. They listen to others fervently and wholeheartedly. They make them feel that they are essential. They work with all parties to create a solution and keep them informed throughout the process (Meador, D. 2017; Ferrell, R.S 2016; Guardacasa et al. 2020).

Fair and Consistent

To solve instructional issues in school, leaders must be fair in dealing with every group member. The participant emphasized the importance of being honest and consistent in every decision. It is also stressed by Meador D. (2017) that an effective school leader leads by example. Leaders understand that others continuously watch what they do and respond to certain conditions. They arrive early in the morning and stay late in the evening. Amid the chaos, a leader maintains their composure. A leader offers assistance and support in places where it is required. They maintain a professional and dignified demeanor both within and outside the institution. They make every effort to make well-informed decisions beneficial to their institution. They can admit when they have made a mistake (Kolodziejczyk, J. 2015; Kearney et al. 2016).

Teachers' Reaction

Teachers reacted differently to the methods indicated above for reinforcing educational concerns:

Submissive

The participant's response shows that the teachers he managed were very submissive. It implies that teachers at that school are really committed and willingly working. Commitment to the teaching profession allows teachers to change their teaching practices to facilitate the classroom. Enhanced job performance is a crucial criterion for establishing an effective learning environment for students in which students are engaged in learning (Altun, M. 2017; Bafadal et al. 2018; Ancho, I.V 2020)

Respectful and Obedient

Aside from being submissive, the study also reflected that teacher in participants' schools are respectful and obedient. They deal with the problem with respect. This view was close related to Meador, D. (2017), an effective school leader is well recognized. A leader appreciates that respect is something that is earned certainly over time. They do not impose on others around them to respect them. Instead, they deserve others' respect by giving consideration. Leaders provide others around them the opportunities to be their best. People almost always listen to highly respected leaders, even if they may not always agree with them. As their teachers respect their orders, they are followed with happiness and contentment. Zubair, et. al 2015; Wu, et. al 2017; Susanti, et. al 2020).

Hesitated

It is undeniable that some teachers responded negatively due to their severe responsibilities. They hesitate to follow orders due to the uncontrolled number of papers works and the burden of printing modules. One issue is that teachers who go the extra mile beyond the call of duty can only win the demand for media platforms. Teachers must be versatile enough to cope with the significant changes brought by this new typical setting (Cho et al. 2019; Zubair et al. 2015; Rasheed et al. 2020).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Ways of Assisting Teachers in Professional Growth

The participants responded on how they assisted their teachers in their professional growth. The following are their responses:

Encouragement

Teachers are the source of knowledge, or the students surround them. It is the work of the school head to update teachers' professional development by encouraging them to attend seminars and workshops. An effective school leader creates those around them better. A mentor works hard to make every teacher better. They inspire them to grow constantly and develop. They challenge their teachers, create goals, and give continuing support. They organize meaningful professional development and training for their staff (Meador, D. 2017; Randel et al. 2018; Muteswa, R. 2016)

Post Conference/ Follow Up

An effective leader always sets standards on how to follow up the performance of its staff. Close supervision must apply to carry out the optimal ability of every teacher. The role of the school head as supervision brings a positive outlook to teachers to do better every day since they are monitored and followed up regularly. Teachers must be evaluated and given technical assistance as they need it. It is the function of the school head to follow up on the guidelines implemented by the school to supervise the full implementation (Susanti et al. 2020; Ngole et al. 2021; Fiarman, 2017)

Factors Affecting Conduct of Seminars

Seminars and workshops are essential factors in professional development, but the participants responded with some hindrances in implementing it in their locality.

Inaccessibility

Conduction of seminars/workshops is essential to teachers' professional development. But due to the threat of the virus, the conduction of seminars/workshop is too limited. Training and development can improve the quality of that output, a more highly trained. The employee is more competent at the job and more aware of the significance of their action. But it is different from standard school years; conduction o seminars required to follow the standard set by IATF (Korkko et al. 2016; Avidov-Ungar, O. 2016; Kennedy, M.M 2016).

The Comfort of Few in Numbers

Training and development improve the organization's ability to cope with change; the successful implementation of change, whether technical or strategic, relies on the skill of the organization's members. The standard set by IATF, the social distancing, is beneficial to the schools composed of few numbers. It is easy to manage and easily comply with the requirements (Patton et al. 2015; Korkko et al. 2016; Mulang, A. 2015).

Inadequate Resources

Aside from internet issues and following standards set by IATF, the limited school resources o school may also hinder the implementation of seminars and training, as stated by the participant's response. According to Whitworth et al. (2015), conducting workshops need to be planned and prepared to meet the required task to fulfill. Due to the shit of curriculum from face to face to modular, funds were allocated on module production as stated in the participant's response.

Developed Follow Up Plans

The following are the developed follow-up plans of participants to improve the performance of their staff.

Faculty Development

Everyone must establish expectations for what their professors should be. The conduct of inset seminars, training, and SLAC sessions is emphasized, as reflected in the participants' comments. An efficient school leader makes those around them better. A mentor works hard to make every teacher better. They inspire them to grow constantly and improve. They challenge their teachers, create goals, and give continuing support to them (Meador, D. 2017; Ngole et al. 2021; Whitworth et al. 2015).

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

Learners Development

One of the responses focused on students' development. When the class resumes facing, her goal is to focus on learners' achievement motivated by excellent classroom management of the teachers. The role and impact of the teacher in students' development are very significant. The effectiveness of teachers' teaching strategies matters most to the learners' understanding of the matter being discussed (Mart, C. T 2017; Jermittoparsert, K. 2020; Collie, R.J 20210).

View about Being a School Head

The following are the participants' responses on how they feel the importance of their school heads and how they evaluated their process.

Deeply Committed

In the study of Francisco et al. (2020), one of the findings noted that the Department of Education is filled with teachers and school administrators who are unselfish to commit themselves to continue learning despite this COVID-19 pandemic. The same responses noted from the participants stated that they evaluate themselves as being engaged despite struggling. Their function as school head makes them more responsible. They also learned from many problems they met along the way being school head and learned through experiences when they were still in the classroom before being designated as school head. According to Daresh et al. (2015), a good leader always displays genuine commitment and dedication to motivate teachers and learners.

More Responsible

As the response from the participants, it was reflected that they consider their function as school head as to be more responsible as the school experiencing difficulties due to the health threat of a pandemic. On Meador, D. (2017) idea about being a school head, he emphasized that a good school leader makes challenging decisions. Leaders are always under the microscope. They are applauded for their school's successes and inspected for their failures. A leader will make tough decisions that can lead to scrutiny. They know that not every decision is the same, and even cases with resemblances may need to be treated differently. They assess each student discipline case individually and listen to all sides (Daresh et al., 2015).

Learned from Problems Met

An effective school leader acknowledges when they make a mistake. A leader endeavors for excellence with the perception that they are not perfect. They know that they are going to make mistakes. When they do make a mistake, they own up to that mistake. A leader works hard to resolve any issues that arise due to an error. The most significant thing that a leader learns from their mistake is that it should not be repeated (Meador, D. 2017; Cabral et al. 2020; Bozkurt et al. 2020)

Learns through Experience

Being compared by experiences in a school setting is always a problem for the school principal. Teachers sometimes throwback the issue to the school head for not being responsive as if they did not undergo being classroom teachers. The participant quoted the importance of his experience as a classroom teacher leading the whole school. Leaders need to be educated about and gain experience in a diversity of leadership styles at the moment when the situational need crisis (Shufutinsky et al. 2020; Solangi, G.M 2017, Uko, E. S 2015)

View About Instructional Leadership in New Normal

Different changes in routine also brought different ideas on how the participants viewed their leadership styles during the pandemic. They stated it as follows:

Inspiring Others

An inspirational leader commonly shows action than telling it. One of the participants' goals in this new normal is to inspire others through his leadership style. According to Mohammed et al. (2017), leaders who maintain a harmonious working relationship positively impact their performance. The point deducted from this is that effectiveness in leadership style affects workers' performance in the organizations. Because the organization and its members work as a system, the

International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp: (55-89), Month: March - April 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

aggregate of individual aims of all organizational members is the overall target of the organization (Randel et al. 2018, Patton et al. 2015)

Provide Support and Vision

The most crucial reason school leaders stimulate and promote involvement is to achieve the organization's goals. However, it must be made evident and fully understood by everyone. Individuals who consistently reach their goals contribute to achieving the overarching corporate goal. As a consequence, when an organization's overall mark is confronted regularly, the result is corporate growth (Mohammed et al. 2017; Muteswa, R. 2016; Peters, R. S 2015)

Effective Role Model

The participant stated that he always wants to be a role model through his action and decision-making. An effective school leader leads by example. A leader understands that others continuously watch what they do and respond to particular circumstances. They arrive early and stay late. A leader remains calm in times where there may be confusion. A leader volunteers to help and assist in areas where they are needed. They carry themselves inside and outside the school with professionalism and dignity where the situation requires it. They do their best to make knowledgeable decisions that will benefit their school (Meador, D. 2017; Bushardt et al. 2018; Francisco et al. 2020).

Limitations

The findings of this study cannot be generalized since it is limited only to providing responses on instructional leadership of the six elementary school heads of Tupi South District for the year 2020-2021. This study explores how elementary school heads of Tupi South District experienced their instructional leadership in the new normal. Its scope was narrowed by findings not intended for generalizations to other settings.

Implication for Future Research

The result of the study could not generate a generalization of the participants' experiences. Consequently, a similar analysis might be undertaken using other research locations to confirm the study's findings.

Moreover, future research may be done to re-interview some of the study participants to see whether their views, feelings, and perceived effects of instructional management have changed over time. And to determine the scope of the problem and provide intervention to address such other methods of research may deem beneficial.

Overall Significance of the Study

The result of the study serves as a reference to different individuals. School Administrators can use the results of this study as a guide in understanding the school instructional leadership of elementary school heads in this new normal. Teachers may also use the findings to deepen their understanding of how the school heads struggle to manage the schools in new normal. Parents and learners can have the privilege of understanding the participants' experiences and hardships to provide excellent service. Other researchers may get valuable insights to explore more gaps and knowledge to understand instructional leadership in this new standard better.

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